

Open Coding on Students Feedback

Question	ID	Answer	Quote	Code
Did you use or not use the anti-pattern catalog for MFE during the evaluation exercise? If so, how? If not, why did you not use it?	P1	I used it. I opened the catalog and read the described problems because, as they are anti-patterns, it means it is very likely that the problem I have is similar to one that has already occurred before, and then I just needed to read the solution to see if it was what I wanted to solve the initial problem.	I opened the catalog and read the described problems because, as they are anti-patterns, it means it is very likely that the problem I have is similar to one that has already occurred before read the solution to see if it was what I wanted to solve the initial problem	Identify common problems Check if the solution is suitable
	P2	I used it to review certain concepts.	review certain concepts	Review MFE concepts
	P3	Yes, the catalog helped a lot because, besides explaining the anti-patterns, it showed a practical example and then the solution to the problem, which greatly helped in identifying how I would solve the proposed problems.	it showed a practical example and then the solution to the problem, which greatly helped in identifying how I would solve the proposed problems.	Identify problems by examples
	P4	I used it; with it, it was possible to have a description of common problems in MFE implementation and their solutions.	it was possible to have a description of common problems in MFE implementation and their solutions	Identify common problems
	P5	Yes, I was looking for problems similar to those presented in the exercise, and after that, I saw how they were solved. Of course, even with similar problems, some solutions proved to be very incompatible.	I was looking for problems similar to those presented in the exercise	Identify problems similar to the presented
			even with similar problems, some solutions proved to be very incompatible	Identify problems by solutions
	P6	Yes, I used it because it helped me understand the problems and know how to solve them in the best possible way.	it helped me understand the problems and know how to solve them in the best possible way	Understand common challenges
	P7	Yes, confirming what I learned in class and knowing how to better segment problems found in MFE. It allowed me to address these problems and made it easier to make decisions.	confirming what I learned in class	Review MFE concepts
			how to better segment problems found in MFE. It allowed me to address these problems and made it easier to make decisions.	Guide architectural decisions
	P8	Yes, as an aid to understanding some issues and developing their solutions.	understanding some issues	Understand common challenges
			developing their solutions	Solving common problems
	P9	Yes, I used it to solve scenarios that can occur in the development of an MFE-oriented architecture.	I used it to solve scenarios that can occur in the development of an MFE	Solving common problems
	P10	Yes, I used it to identify the problems and the solutions to the respective questions.	identify the problems and the solutions to the respective questions	Identify problems and solutions
	P11	I used it a lot, seeking to understand the different types of anti-patterns and their possible solutions. It makes problems that can be prevented much more visible before a product is 80%-100% complete, avoiding rework.	seeking to understand the different types of anti-patterns and their possible solutions	Understand common challenges
			It makes problems that can be prevented much more visible before a product is 80%-100% complete, avoiding rework.	Prevent problems
	P12	Yes, checking solutions for the problems I encountered during the exercise and seeing examples and descriptions helped me understand the problem in some questions.	checking solutions for the problems I encountered during the exercise	Identify problems and solutions
			seeing examples and descriptions helped me understand the problem in some questions	Understand problems by examples
	P13	Yes, I used it a lot to understand if the situation proposed by the question resembled any example described by the anti-patterns. Besides analyzing my possible architectural decisions, avoiding falling into a possible listed case.	understand if the situation proposed by the question resembled any example described by the anti-patterns.	Identify problems by examples
			possible architectural decisions, avoiding falling into a possible listed case	Guide architectural decisions
	P14	Yes, I used it; it served as a reminder.	it served as a reminder	Review MFE concepts
	P15	Yes, analyzing the addressed problems and the examples cited in the catalog to associate them with the scenario proposed in the exercise.	analyzing the addressed problems and the examples cited in the catalog to associate them with the scenario	Identify problems by examples
	P16	Yes, it helped me a lot when answering the questions because I could identify the problems that appeared as anti-patterns.	I could identify the problems that appeared as anti-patterns	Identify problems and solutions
	P17	I used it. It was very useful to see how the presented problems fit into the anti-patterns. Seeing the anti-patterns in practice increased my knowledge about the subject.	useful to see how the presented problems fit into the anti-patterns	Identify common problems
Seeing the anti-patterns in practice increased my knowledge about the subject			Learn based on practical problems	
P18	Yes, I looked at the descriptions on the homepage. I checked if there was something similar to what I wanted, clicked to confirm through the example, and used the solution if that was the case.	I checked if there was something similar to what I wanted	Identify problems similar to the presented	
		clicked to confirm through the example	Identify problems by examples	
P19	Yes, to check if any of the examples were in the catalog, considering that the catalog contains the most common anti-patterns, I believe it is useful to consult it to avoid errors that have already been documented.	to check if any of the examples were in the catalog	Identify problems and solutions	
		avoid errors that have already been documented.	Prevent problems	
P20	I used it as a reference to see if someone had already reported the same problem and how they solved it.	reference to see if someone had already reported the same problem and how they solved it	Identify common problems	
P21	Yes, it helped me identify problems and demonstrate the best solutions.	identify problems and demonstrate the best solutions.	Identify problems and solutions	
P22	Yes, I used it to identify the proposed problems in the questions.	identify the proposed problems in the questions	Identify problems and solutions	
P23	Yes, I used it a lot. When faced with questions about changing the architecture, I often found myself consulting the catalog.	When faced with questions about changing the architecture, I often found myself consulting the catalog	Guide architectural decisions	
Did you notice benefits or challenges when using the anti-pattern catalog for MFE? Ease or difficulties of use? If so, what were they?	P1	Benefits and conveniences. Since the catalog has several short descriptions of problems that have occurred before, it is very productive to check if the problem I face is in the catalog to see the solution other developers had, instead of thinking of one on my own.	catalog has several short descriptions of problems that have occurred before, it is very productive to check if the problem I face is in the catalog to see the solution other developers had	Identify common problems
	P3	Using the catalog helped standardize MFE creation, as I could see possible errors that could occur when creating an MFE and avoid them.	helped standardize MFE creation, as I could see possible errors that could occur when creating an MFE and avoid them	Guide architectural decisions
	P4	I had difficulties understanding the description of each anti-pattern; I had to open all of them to see the description. There could be a summary in each card of the catalogs on the main screens.	difficulties understanding the description of each anti-pattern; I had to open all of them to see the description. There could be a summary in each card of the catalogs on the main screens	Consult several anti-patterns at once
	P5	The benefits were the solutions shown in each concept, which are straightforward.	solutions shown in each concept, which are straightforward	Check straightforward solutions
	P6	Yes. As benefits, I noticed it is easy to understand and has great examples of occurrences that help us understand the correct way we can proceed.	easy to understand and has great examples of occurrences that help us understand the correct way we can proceed	Understand problems by examples

P7	Yes, conveniences because it is easy to visualize, especially with the use of categories. However, one thing is that I believe some situations are not very clear. Maybe there is no anti-pattern that explicitly shows the problem, but their combination can clarify what needs to be done.	it is easy to visualize, especially with the use of categories I believe some situations are not very clear. Maybe there is no anti-pattern that explicitly shows the problem, but their combination can clarify what needs to be done	Consult by categories Linking anti-patterns	
P8	The benefits I noticed were that it was an easy, quick, and accessible way to obtain information. A challenge was that some examples were not very clear, and I had to reread them several times.	an easy, quick, and accessible way to obtain information some examples were not very clear, and I had to reread them several times	Review MFE concepts Understand problems by examples	
P9	It is very intuitive, easy to navigate, with simple and direct examples followed by their respective solutions. It is a great tool.			
P10	Conveniences. The anti-pattern catalog is very intuitive. That way, I had no difficulties locating anything. Moreover, its division into concept, example, and solution greatly facilitates understanding.	its division into concept, example, and solution greatly facilitates understanding	Understand by structured anti-patterns	
P11	Benefits and conveniences. Interaction is very easy, and having the material with the set definition, example, and solution is much more intuitive and positive.			
P12	Benefits because with the descriptions, I was able to identify the problems during the exercises, as well as possible solutions, and it was very easy to use, very intuitive.	with the descriptions, I was able to identify the problems during the exercises, as well as possible solutions	Identify problems and solutions	
P13	I believe the biggest challenge is the amount of text present. Perhaps using more images for the examples would be more effective.	the biggest challenge is the amount of text present. Perhaps using more images for the examples would be more effective	Understand by image	
P14	The only negative point I noticed was that the anti-pattern tags were not very useful, at least for the exercise we did.			
P15	Benefits due to the clarity presented in the catalog and convenience because it was possible to associate the exercise context with the contexts, descriptions, and solutions shown in the catalog.	possible to associate the exercise context with the contexts, descriptions, and solutions shown in the catalog	Identify problems similar to the presented	
P16	It was very easy to use; the explanations were good, especially those with images.	the explanations were good, especially those with images	Understand by image	
P17	I found it easy to use.			
P18	Yes, benefits, the site is very direct in what it proposes.			
P19	I noticed benefits because, for me, it is more advantageous to avoid an error that is already documented than to end up reproducing an error that is already documented. The main conveniences I observed were: a practical example of the anti-patterns, their solution, and the categorization.	more advantageous to avoid an error that is already documented than to end up reproducing an error that is already documented a practical example of the anti-patterns, their solution	Prevent problems Understand problems by examples	
P20	Several benefits due to the simplicity of the page and its objectivity. However, navigation bothered me a bit. If I perform a filtered search and return to the previous page, I go to where all are, not where the filters are. Another thing that could help is that, when opening an anti-pattern, the page could show others from the same topic or similar ones at the bottom.	when opening an anti-pattern, the page could show others from the same topic or similar ones at the bottom.	Linking anti-patterns	
P21	Ease of use.			
P22	Benefits and conveniences. It is simple to consult, and the examples helped me identify the problem	and the examples helped me identify the problem	Identify problems by examples	
P23	Initially, it was in English, and that made it a bit difficult, but I found that the button filters helped a lot. I practically did not use the search input at the top of the screen.	I found that the button filters helped a lot	Consult by categories	
Describe here if and how the anti-pattern catalog for MFE helped or hindered your learning about Micro Frontends.	P1	It helped because various problems and solutions are documented, thus contributing to sharing solutions for recurring problems instead of leaving the developer to think of a solution on their own.	various problems and solutions are documented, thus contributing to sharing solutions for recurring problems	Identify common problems
	P2	It provided a simpler and faster way to access information about the anti-patterns.	simpler and faster way to access information about the anti-patterns	Review MFE concepts
	P3	The catalog helped me learn about MFE because, in it, I saw possible errors that can occur in MFE creation and how to solve these problems.	learn about MFE because, in it, I saw possible errors that can occur in MFE creation and how to solve these problems	Learn based on practical problems
	P4	It helped by centralizing content about MFEs. However, the catalog could include summaries and slides presented in the classes, as I believe the purpose of the catalog would be to centralize MFE content. This way, it would be friendlier to new users.	helped by centralizing content about MFEs. However, the catalog could include summaries and slides presented in the classes	Review MFE concepts
	P5	A better description of the problems and solutions in the catalog helped me a lot to draw a parallel with the problems proposed in the activity.	better description of the problems and solutions in the catalog helped me a lot to draw a parallel with the problems proposed in the activity	Identify problems by solutions
	P6	Yes, it helped. I confess that it was even a bit easier to understand the anti-pattern catalog than the design patterns I learned in Assignment 2. But understanding the subject became easier, and I was able to learn and will try to use these patterns and anti-patterns in my future projects.	easier to understand the anti-pattern catalog than the design patterns I learned in Assignment 2 will try to use these patterns and anti-patterns in my future projects	Understand common challenges Guide architectural decisions
	P7	It helped describe better the problems encountered and how to solve them. I missed more examples and visual elements, which help to remember each anti-pattern.	describe better the problems encountered and how to solve them missed more examples and visual elements, which help to remember each anti-pattern	Identify problems and solutions Understand by image
	P8	It helped me understand in an organized, clear, and effective way. By reading the problem, I could easily choose which anti-pattern to use.	understand in an organized, clear, and effective way reading the problem, I could easily choose which anti-pattern to use	Understand by structured anti-patterns Identify problems and solutions
	P9	It helped me because it helped me avoid common mistakes that I would definitely have made if I did not know about them.	avoid common mistakes that I would definitely have made if I did not know about them	Prevent problems
	P10	With a good division in the catalog, I was able to understand, given that the way it is divided allows me to associate and identify the anti-patterns more easily.	given that the way it is divided allows me to associate and identify the anti-patterns more easily.	Understand by structured anti-patterns
	P11	It helped in problem abstraction. It became much easier to visualize and solve possible problems.	It became much easier to visualize and solve possible problems	Identify common problems
	P12	It helped, especially with practical examples and solutions for each type of anti-pattern.	especially with practical examples and solutions for each type of anti-pattern	Understand problems by examples
	P13	It helped a lot because, with it, I could understand real situations and challenges faced during architectural decisions of a system with MFEs.	I could understand real situations and challenges faced during architectural decisions of a system with MFEs	Understand common challenges
	P14	It helped, but I believe the classes were more important for my understanding; the catalog served as a review.	the catalog served as a review	Review MFE concepts

	P16	The catalog helped because it was very explanatory regarding common errors in MFE architecture.		
	p17	It helped a lot. It is good to see what we should not do when developing software.	good to see what we should not do when developing software	Prevent problems
	P18	After reading a problem description, checking if that problem is caused by a design issue helps a lot because then I can already see if it can be solved in a way that has already been experimented with by someone more experienced than me.	After reading a problem description, checking if that problem is caused by a design issue helps a lot because then I can already see if it can be solved in a way that has already been experimented	Identify problems and solutions
	p19	The catalog helped me identify common patterns that could be harmful to me in the future, potentially causing an error in a project's architecture, as it describes, exemplifies, and suggests a solution for these anti-patterns.	identify common patterns that could be harmful to me in the future, potentially causing an error in a project's architecture	Prevent problems
	P20	It helped especially when contextualizing myself with the problem. Many times, I had difficulty identifying problems because I did not know all the problems, whether it was indeed a problem, and if it was, how would I solve it? All these questions were greatly minimized by using the catalog. The catalog helped me diagnose problems I did not previously know.	I had difficulty identifying problems because I did not know all the problems, whether it was indeed a problem, and if it was, how would I solve it? All these questions were greatly minimized by using the catalog. The catalog helped me diagnose problems I did not previously know.	Identify problems and solutions Identify common problems
	P21	MFE catalog helped me remember some concepts I did not recall, in addition to being very clear in its explanations and using examples.	helped me remember some concepts I did not recall being very clear in its explanations and using examples	Review MFE concepts Understand problems by examples
	P22	It helped me due to the ease of accessing the anti-patterns that I probably would not have if I were searching for them on websites.	ease of accessing the anti-patterns that I probably would not have if I were searching for them on websites	Identify common problems
	P23	The catalog helped a lot when looking for categories of anti-patterns. It was a bit inconvenient to translate from English to Portuguese.	The catalog helped a lot when looking for categories of anti-patterns	Consult by categories
Do you have any suggestions for improving the anti-pattern catalog for MFEs? If you encountered any difficulty understanding the definition of an anti-pattern (considering the fields for problem, solution, and example), please indicate which anti-pattern it was and describe what was unclear.	P3	Availability of translation into other languages increases accessibility for people who do not master English very well.		
	P4	As I mentioned in the previous response, it would be possible to add summaries and slides presented in the classes to the catalog, as I believe the purpose of the catalog is to centralize MFE-related content, making it more user-friendly for new users.	add summaries and slides presented in the classes to the catalog	Review MFE concepts
	P5	If there is at least one more scenario as an application example, that would be ideal.	at least one more scenario as an application example, that would be ideal	Understand problems by examples
	P6	More figures and, if possible, code examples in any language.	More figures code examples in any language	Understand by image Understand problems by examples
	P7	I suggest adding more visual elements and more examples for each anti-pattern, as well as a description of the 'domain' of the category	adding more visual elements more examples for each anti-pattern	Understand by image Understand problems by examples
	P8	I did not understand the Micro Frontend Knot very well.		
	p9	I might have missed it, but I could not find the anti-pattern that addresses error handling. If it is indeed not present in the catalog, I believe its inclusion would be a good addition. However, I might have just failed to locate it.		
	P10	Only adding of more anti-patterns for other types of systems.		
	P13	I believe using more visual resources could be very helpful to avoid the overwhelming amount of text in each listed anti-pattern.	using more visual resources could be very helpful to avoid the overwhelming amount of text	Understand by image
	P14	Within the definitions of the anti-patterns, I did not find any difficulty in understanding.		
	p16	It is a good catalog as it is, but the use of images in some explanations helped more than just text.	but the use of images in some explanations helped more than just text	Understand by image
	p19	I believe a dictionary of key terms related to architecture in the catalog could facilitate understanding, but it was easy to use.	dictionary of key terms related to architecture in the catalog could facilitate understanding	Identify problems by keywords
	P21	The catalog is perfect, no improvements are needed.		
	P22	Perhaps more examples and bibliographic references where it is possible to delve deeper into the anti-patterns.	more examples bibliographic references where it is possible to delve deeper into the anti-patterns	Understand problems by examples Review MFE concepts